

SOCIAL SCIENCES

PECULIARITIES AND PROSPECTS OF ECOLOGICAL EDUCATION AT PRESCHOOLS OF KAZAKHSTAN

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Abstract

The article discusses the goals and methods of environmental education in preschool institutions of Kazakhstan. At a time when the issue of ecology is becoming increasingly important for modern society, a special role is assigned to preschool organizations. The article emphasizes the importance of preschool institutions in the formation of ecological culture, highlights important steps such as using gaming technology, creative activity that lay the foundation for raising children in harmony with nature.

Keywords: ecological education, sustainable development, preschool, environment, ecology

Environmental education of a preschool institution is considered one of the directions of sustainable development. The main goal of the preschool institution is the safety of the child's life. And the main goal of environmental education is the formation of an ecological attitude, consciousness, great common sense, responsibility, attitude to nature of the younger generation. Through this upbringing, a person's sense of culture and environmental consciousness are formed. Preschool is the period when the child's worldview is formed. Environmental education given at this young age increases children's responsibility for nature, teaches them to protect the environment, the formation of environmental behavior. Instilling ecology in the child's mind, teaching him to follow environmental orders will not only lay the foundation for nature conservation, but will allow in the future to educate a generation that is more environmentally friendly and empathetic [1].

The main goal of environmental education in kindergarten is to awaken children's interest in living in harmony with nature, increase their environmental knowledge and form an ecological culture. There are several main tasks of these areas of education:

- Education about nature and the environment;
- Development of love for nature, care;
- Formation of environmental skills such as energy saving, water saving;
- Teach children to take responsibility for environmental issues [2].

In addition, information technologies are also used in the implementation of environmental education. It is effective to introduce children to the problem of ecology through electronic textbooks, video content, vertical excursions. Strengthen the child's relationship with nature through environmental games and practices. Control is the only way to form environmental education in kindergarten. Every time children go for a walk, observing nature, they see many different phenomena. On the basis of this, the ability not only to observe children, but also to show the connections of objects and phenomena. In the process of control, it is necessary to

guide the activities of preschool children, ask questions and set them problematic tasks.

The main thing is to awaken an emotional reaction in children and the desire to continue such actions on their own. For example, if we control the strong wind and control the scattering of the surrounding area, we can give an example of the role of humanity in organizing its collection. At the same time, the presence of animals and plants in kindergarten, which children themselves observe and care for, teaches them to take care of the environment, love for work and get used to it, and gradually such qualities as responsibility for the assigned task were formed in the child. "Corner of Nature", which brings closer to nature in the preschool organization. In a corner of nature, children not only observe, but also defend various experimental projects. From the same projects can show the laws of nature, its benefits and harms to humanity.

The child's concern for nature from an early age can be realized through this observation and experimental work. Will the great thinker of the Kazakh people A. Kunanbayev be a child who will grow up without playing games and singing?- as they say, the game occupies a special place in the life of a child. The game helps preschoolers develop their personality, develop their language, learn literacy, and get closer to friends. After all, the means of educating a child from infancy to honesty, courage, kindness, and work are games. The fate of the future society also directly depends on the upbringing of this child. It is these children who are both developing and advancing in society. The first educational ladder, which establishes simple skills in the child's mind that solve a wide variety of problems of upbringing, is kindergarten. [3] For the general purpose of environmental education, it is written that it is possible to lay the foundations of environmental culture in preschool age, based on the peculiarities of the development of child psychology, at this stage bright, figurative emotional impressions, the first natural science concepts, form the basis of the correct attitude to the environment and value orientations in it.

Comprehensive work on environmental education of preschool children is an important aspect of their development, which is characterized by the formation of environmental awareness, a responsible attitude to nature and a healthy lifestyle. The preschool organization plays a key role in educating children about nature conservation and teaching them a responsible attitude to nature. [4] The problem of the relationship between man and the environment and the implementation of specific measures to protect and preserve natural resources today becomes not only an independent task of each state, each country, but also a national problem that all states unite, unite and unite. This led to the creation of an environmental International Society of different countries.

It has become one of the most important issues discussed by the United Nations. Protecting natural resources is not about not using them at all, but rather about using them carefully, efficiently and not allowing waste. Affordable and high-quality preschool education is included in the list of 17 Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations (UN). The state policy in the system of preschool education and training is aimed at creating conditions for children from different social groups and families with different living conditions to have equal initial opportunities and receive a quality education.

Over the past 10 years, the issue of covering children with preschool education and training has been largely resolved. Today, the preschool is:

- not only a place to take care of the child and look after him, but also a developing educational environment, which primarily and mainly creates comfortable and safe conditions, aimed at comprehensively meeting the needs of children;
- make children healthy, intellectual, moral, emotional, partner of the family in matters of Social Development;
- every teacher is a territory of joy and well-being, which is a friend of the child and an assistant in his development.

This position should become the foundation of preschool institutions. Assessment of the quality of preschool education and training to determine the quality of pre-school education, since 2017, the development, approval and implementation of the system of indicators (monitoring) (methodological principles, 2018) for the development of skills and abilities of children who have not reached the school conducted by the preschool institution itself has begun in Kazakhstan. This monitoring is important for regulating the process of raising and educating children. The internal assessment of the quality of preschool education includes its own assessment, which provides for the collection and analysis of materials on the professional activities of teachers and the effectiveness of the educational environment. It provides for the stages of monitoring the development of preschool children, the formation of skills and flexibility of children in accordance with age characteristics, the introduction of actions that regulate the work process of the teacher.

Children's abilities and acquired skills are reflected in the child's development card. This tool for in-

ternal evaluation is maintained. Assessment of the quality of preschool education includes independent assessment and voluntary institutional accreditation through state certification, which includes a certificate between parents.[5] External monitoring of kindergartens is carried out only in order to ensure the quality standard of education and safety of children. For the same purpose, the requirements for the procedure for opening and monitoring the activities of a preschool institution on issues of safety, ensuring the rights of children and their legal representatives in accordance with the legislation of the Republic of Kazakhstan will be revised. It is necessary to create a system of quality assurance of preschool education, which determines the level of training of teachers, permission to work with children and the conditions created for the early development of children. In case of violation of the rights and legitimate interests of children based on the results of an external assessment, information is transferred to the

Committee for the protection of children's rights. Issues of restoring children's rights, ensuring comfortable living conditions are considered at interdepartmental meetings of the commission on juvenile affairs under Representative and local executive bodies. Thus, a comprehensive system of Independent National Assessment of the quality of preschool education is formed using the ECERS early childhood environment Rating Scale, which is used in the world as a comprehensive assessment tool.[6] In conclusion, for our own children, whether they are in kindergartens, study at school, college or university, national goals, educational aspirations in terms of what we want should be an incentive for a wide discussion of society. The time has come to establish a public agreement between the state and society in order to determine the real nationwide priorities of Education, which we all dream of for the future of our children, and equally distribute responsibility for the development of the industry.

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